

FundMount Platform for Crowd-Sourcing : A Web Application

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ABSTRACT

Crowd-sourcing is process which includes overall population to give seed cash to new recommendation. Crowd-sourcing model comprises three sorts of performers which incorporate venture initiator, people of gatherings and a directing association. The venture initiator brings the new thought to get subsidized, people or gatherings underpins that thought, and directing association which unites parties all to execute thought, and directing association which unites parties all to execute thought. Utilizing crowd-sourcing strategy new pursuits and new entrepreneurs can get the financing to fire up their tasks and actualizes the new thoughts which can be valuable to the overall population or to the organization holders or whatever other endeavors. Crowd-sourcing is the procedure through which the venture holders/proprietors can get funding's from the overall population and actualizes that venture.

KEYWORDS: funding, backers, pledge, crowd-sourcing, activity diagram.

I. INTRODUCTION

Crowd-sourcing is the way toward requesting the reserve the people in general for the new businesses and the new thoughts/ventures. It gives stage to new dares to get supported to fire up another venture. FundMount is the site which gives the crowd-sourcing stage to the dares to get stores from the overall population of their new ventures. FundMount site gives stage to new pursuits through which they can transfer their thoughts/extends as picture, video. The venture proprietors can transfer their undertakings through class astute there are numerous classifications through which clients can transfer their tasks. The client of the site can see that picture or video of thought/venture that endeavors make finance for that thought/extend. The FundMount site gives online installment office through which clients can make supports through on the web. The proprietors of the

venture needs to set the subsidizing time of the venture on site is greater 60 days and he ought to give the sum which ought to be financed to actualize that venture. At the point when the proprietor of the venture sets the store term till that span that financing sum ought to be accomplished else it will be disposed of and the supported sum won't be give to the proprietor of venture and the sum will be come back to the funders. There is one approach if the financing sum is accomplished up-to 90% then that sum will be hand-over to the venture proprietor. At the point when the objective of the venture is accomplished through the financing then the site will charge 5% of that subsidizing add up to keep up the site.

FundMount gives one gainful approach to the funders as indicated by the scope of subsidizing sum. There is one social cause class in which the venture proprietors can refresh the thoughts for the social cause which is gainful to the general public for which the site won't charge the essential 5% measure of the effectively accomplished financing sum.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

A. Existing System :

The framework has the site for crowd-sourcing where clients can make their record on the site and transfers their activities class astute the current framework restricted to remote a nation which is not for India.

B. Proposed System :

In the proposed The framework is crowd-sourcing site where clients can enlist free and log in and transfer their thoughts/extends on the site to get subsidized from general individuals. This site is just for the India nation. The site gives different sorts of classifications to transfer the activities with the classifications there is one social cause classification in which clients can transfer the tasks which is valuable for the general public and for this classification the site sick not

charge the expenses for different classes if the store is accomplished then the sum is handover-ed to the venture proprietor and the 5% of the reserve is taken for the site advancement.

C. Technical Description :

The technologies used to implement the website is PHP, jQuery, JavaScript. The connection between these technologies are PHP is a scripting language used to develop the code for the website and javascript is used for the scripting operations to validate the working and the flow of the pages. These technologies are connected altogether technically without PHP javascript and jQuery cannot be implemented and both these are used within PHP to validate the PHP working. Validation for the log in, register and for the validate dates and other features are executed by javascript/jquery. Scripting is to develop the phenomena of the website for the responsive working of validating the results.

III. IMPLEMENTATION

Crowd-sourcing frameworks can be seen as socio-technical frameworks that give educational items and administrations to inner or outside clients by bridling the various capability of vast gatherings of individuals, normally by means of the web. These frameworks utilize varieties of a non specific crowd-sourcing process that depends principally on commitments from human members to change existing or deliver new data. Data innovation is utilized to empower this procedure and, where conceivable, bolster the exercises performed in the framework. A crowd-sourcing procedure begins with a crowd-sourcing association, frequently called requester, that distributes an open call for interest in a specific assignment to the swarm, i.e., to a commonly unlimited gathering of potential patrons. In light of this call, an ex-bet obscure subset of people in the group choose in the event that they are willing and fit for adding to the separate undertaking. This fundamental self-selection some portion of the procedure is additionally called "patrons self-id". People that take part present their commitments, which are then accumulated and chosen in various ways, contingent upon the capacity of the crowd-sourcing framework. The open way of their procedures empowers crowd-sourcing frameworks to come to a extensive number of potential donors and,

accordingly, proportional exceptionally well. At the same time, intrigued people may originate from altogether extraordinary foundations, which makes the potential for an abnormal state of assorted qualities in the individual group. It is this remarkable versatility and assorted qualities that, if actualized accurately, guarantee the vast achievement of crowd-sourcing frameworks for an assortment of hierarchical capabilities. A crowd-sourcing procedure depends basically on commitments from the group to give enlightening items and administrations for inward or, then again outside clients.

Figure 1 Activity diagram

The above figure shows the activity diagram of the project. Activity diagram is utilized to describe the dynamic modules of the system. Activity diagram is usually a flowchart to represent the flow from one activity to another activity. The activity can be described as an operation of the module. The control flow is drawn from one operation to another. An activity diagram presents a set of actions and the flow of control in a module.

Technical Queries :

session_write_close();

PHP code for Log in :

```

<?php include('include/connect.php'); ?>
} else {
    session_write_close();
    ?>
<!--<script type="text/javascript">
    alert("Invalid Username or Password");
</script>-->
<?php
    if (isset($_POST['btnlogin'])) {
        /*function clean($str) {
            $str = @trim($str);
            if (get_magic_quotes_gpc()) {
                $str = stripslashes($str);
            }
            return
mysqli_real_escape_string($str);
        } */
        $email = $_POST['txtemail'];
        /*clean*/($email);

        $password=/*clean*/($_POST['txtpassword']);
        $pass=md5($password);

        $query = "select * from signup where
        email='$email' and pass='$pass' " or
        die(mysqli_error());
        $count = mysqli_num_rows($query);
        $row = mysqli_fetch_array($query);
        if ($count > 0) {
            session_start();
            session_regenerate_id();
            $_SESSION['id'] = $row['id'];
            $memid=$row['id'];
            $fname=$row['name'];
            $user=$row['email'];
            date_default_timezone_set('Asia/Kolkata');
            $date=date('F j, Y g:i: a ');

            //echo
            "<script>window.location.replace('strataproject.php')
            </script>";

            echo ("<script>alert('Login
            Successful')</script>");
            echo
            "<script>window.location.replace('strataproject.php')
            </script>";
        } else {
            session_write_close();
            ?>
            <!--<script type="text/javascript">
            alert("Invalid Username or Password");
            </script>-->
            echo ("<script>alert('Invalid
            Username or Password')</script>");
            echo
            "<script>window.location.replace('logregister.php')</
            script>";
        }
    }
}
?>

```

The above script is the log in code for the FundMount website through which users information will be validated and the appropriate error messages or the successful query messages will be displayed.

Code to count days for the Funding duration :

```

<?php
$date = 'may 25 2017';
$exp_date = "var end = new Date('". $date . "');";
$today's_date = date("F j Y g:i:s A T");

if ($today's_date < $exp_date) {
    ?>
<script>
<?php echo $exp_date ;?>

var _second = 1000;
var _minute = _second * 60;
var _hour = _minute * 60;
var _day = _hour *24
var timer;

function showRemaining()
{
    var now = new Date();
    var distance = end - now;
    if (distance < 0) {

```

```

clearInterval( timer );

document.getElementById('countdown').innerHTML
= 'EXPIRED!';

return;
}
var days = Math.floor(distance / _day);
/*var hours = Math.floor( (distance % _day ) /
_hour );
var minutes = Math.floor( (distance % _hour) /
_minute );
var seconds = Math.floor( (distance % _minute) /
_second );*/

```

```

document.getElementById('countdown').innerHTML
= 'Days Left' + days + '<br />';

```

```

/*document.getElementById('countdown').innerHTM
L += 'Hours: ' + hours+ '<br />';

```

```

document.getElementById('countdown').innerHTML
+= 'Minutes: ' + minutes+ '<br />';

```

```

document.getElementById('countdown').innerHTML
+= 'Seconds: ' + seconds+ '<br />';*/
}

```

```

timer = setInterval(showRemaining, 1000);
</script>
<?php
} else {
    echo "Times Up";
}
?>

```

The Funding duration is count by the two dates between the current date and the last date for the funding. The difference between these two dates is counted and displayed as how many days are left to get funded.

Format Money code :

```

<?php
function formatMoney($number, $fractional=false) {
    if ($fractional) {
        $number = sprintf("%.2f", $number);
    }
}

```

```

}
while (true) {
    $replaced = preg_replace('/(-
?d+)(\d\d\d)/', '$1,$2', $number);
    if ($replaced != $number) {
        $number = $replaced;
    } else {
        break;
    }
}
return $number;
}
?>

```

The above PHP, javascript code use to format the money in Indian Rs. The code is used to display funding amount of the project and it is counted whenever the new pledge amount is added into the pledge amount.

RESULTS

FundMount is a website which is platform for new ventures where users can register free and can log in to the website. When user successfully logs in to the website the user can upload their ideas/projects for which they want to get fund. Users are nothing but new ventures who can show their ideas/projects through images/videos. There are number of categories according to which users can upload their projects. Users can also make pledge to other projects if they likes the idea. When user logs in user can start with the project the start a project page will be displayed when the user successfully enters the project title, the category of the project and the permanent residential then user gets the new form to add information about the project the file, title, description, funding amount, funding duration. When the user successfully uploads the information then that uploaded file will be displayed on home page. If the project is successfully funded then 5% of funding amount will be deducted from the total pledged amount.

Modules :

User :

Users can register/log in to the website to get funded for the ideas or can fund to other projects.

Admin :

Admin can log in and view the project lists. New project list, all project list, Funded project list and the users list. New project list contains the upcoming projects if the project is valid and the funding amount is valid then it will be verified by the admin. The verified project will be displayed on the home page.

Sr.No	Test Case	Input supplied	Expected Result	Actual Result	Pass
	Upload Project form for FundMount	Upload file blank	Popup to upload file	Popup to upload file	Yes
		All records not entered	Popup to enter all the fields	Popup to enter all the fields	Yes
		All records entered	Popup record added successfully	Popup record added successfully	Yes
		Any of the field is blank	Popup to enter all the records	Popup to enter all the records	Yes

Table No. 1 Test cases for Upload project

IV. CONCLUSION

In this manner, FundMount will help the general public to transfer their thoughts to get financed and to actualize that thoughts which is valuable to all. The FundMount clients everywhere throughout the India will have the capacity to give the support to the new thoughts through sponsorship the ventures which are transferred on FundMount. It gives an incredible stage to get support for the thoughts to actualize the thoughts.

The prerequisites indicated amid examination stage was met and the customers necessities are likewise fulfilled totally.

The ventures readiness and cost estimation was legitimately overseen and consequently the venture was finished in evaluated time.

The equipment and programming prerequisites indicated were legitimately used being developed of ventures.

FUTURE ENHANCEMENT

This sort of site is as of now grew however not for India. This site is just for India. The classes of the venture thoughts will be expanded.

We will solicit project proprietors to refresh status from the venture which is in creating process in the wake of getting supported by the FundMount.

The refreshed status of the venture will be educated to the patrons of that venture by means of email so no compelling reason to peruse the site for the status.

Extend proprietor will be send welcome to the patrons for sponsorship the venture by means of email. Most saw and most enjoyed venture on the FundMount will get financed from the FundMount and we won't charge the site upkeep charge from the venture proprietor.

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